

THE NAVY OCEAN FACILITIES PROGRAM - A STATUS REPORT
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ABSTRACT

The Navy requires highly reliable and cost effective fixed ocean facilities to support its mission requirements. Design and construction of these ocean structures to meet stringent performance requirements, severe environmental conditions and minimum life cycle cost represents a significant challenge in light of today's constrained resources. The Navy's ocean facilities capability is reviewed in the paper including projects involving design and construction of unique ocean facilities.

INTRODUCTION

In the late 1960's, the Stratton Commission was evolving a plan of action regarding our National Marine Resources and Policy. Concurrently the Navy was focusing attention on defining ocean engineering capability needs to satisfy long term defense requirements. Program plans evolved from this study effort and resources were committed toward improving the Navy's capability to more fully utilize the oceans in support of its missions. One of the programs initiated was directed toward increasing the Navy's capability in the design and construction of fixed ocean facilities.

The Navy as well as industry, particularly the offshore petroleum industry, had been advancing ocean engineering technology in the 1950's and 1960's as new frontiers were confronted. But, advancements in the technology were not without increased risks and failures, some very catastrophic. In ocean construction projects during this period by Navy, industry and institutions, involving even simple structures, one could observe: (1) economic waste in design and construction, (2) immediate structural failure, (3) short structural lifetime, (4) high maintenance costs and (5) structural performance that deters system performance requirements. If the Navy was to perform its mission effectively, improvements in its capability were needed. This requirement gave birth to the Ocean Facilities Program which has become an integral part of the Navy's ocean engineering capability. Established in 1968 and now in its second decade of existence, the Ocean Facilities Program provides the Navy with a capability for reliable and economical acquisition, maintenance and repair of ocean facilities.

OCEAN FACILITY PROGRAM

Under the leadership of Eager¹ the Ocean Facilities Program was structured bringing together elements of the Naval Construction Force and the Naval Material Command to form an integrated capability. The program managed by the Naval Facilities Engineering Command, consists of three equally important and parallel efforts which were integrated into a common thrust to achieve an improved capability. These parallel efforts consist of (1) mission analysis leading to defined Navy longterm ocean facility requirements; (2) capability development through research, design criteria/standards and construction technique development, and acquisition/development of ocean construction equipment based on the above facility requirements; and (3) application of this capability to design and construction of Navy ocean facility requirements.

Over the past decade the Navy's ocean engineering capability has continued to mature and the Navy has become a recognized leader in the ocean facilities industry. The component parts of the Navy's ocean facilities capability development can be visualized as a trident scepter. Integrated and interrelated they form a comprehensive capability consisting of personnel, engineering/technology base and ocean construction equipment. These component parts of the Ocean Facilities Program are briefly described to provide insight into how the Navy is achieving and maintaining capability in ocean engineering.

Personnel

The critical component of any organizational capability is its personnel. Technical demands of a complex engineering discipline require a highly trained and experienced cadre of personnel to have an effective and efficient capability. Recognizing this need, the Navy established sub-specialty career patterns for both military and civilian personnel.

Through a highly competitive process, U.S. Navy Civil Engineer Corps officers are selected for advanced academic training leading to a masters degree in ocean engineering followed by training to qualify as a Navy diving officer. A cadre of approximately thirty officers with various levels of experience are maintained to manage the Navy's ocean facilities business and provide leadership in the acquisition management of high technology underwater systems. Through centralized management these officer personnel are detailed based on their experience level to satisfy the requirements of twenty-two technical and operational positions. Experienced gained in more junior engineering positions qualifies the officer to be assigned to more demanding technical and managerial positions.

Likewise Seabee enlisted personnel with training in various construction trade skills and possessing a modicum of experience are selected for training as Navy divers. Following diving training they receive initially basic and later in their career advanced underwater construction technician training. This training provides them with not only the numerous skills necessary to perform construction work underwater, but also teaches them how to plan and prepare for underwater construction tasks. Once trained these specially skilled Seabees are placed in one of the two operational Underwater Construction Teams (UCTs) which perform ocean construction tasks as assigned by their respective fleet commander. Like the officer community, the enlisted community is also centrally managed to provide a career pattern of positions of ever increasing responsibility and experience. As a result of numerous opportunities for expanded job responsibilities at an early career point and challenging construction projects, personnel retention is one of the highest in the Navy and thus, capability to perform ocean construction remains sound.

The critical mass of the Navy's ocean engineering technical ability is resident in its civilian engineers and technicians. These individuals are centralized in the Ocean Engineering and Construction Project Office, Chesapeake Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command, and in the Ocean Engineering

Department, Naval Civil Engineering Laboratory. Together they provide a highly trained, stable work force of ocean engineers and technicians which augment and support the fleet components, the UCT's.

Recruited from the nations best ocean engineering schools, young engineers pursue a two-three year on-the-job training program to gain experience in ocean engineering design and construction before being placed in a permanent job. Depending on the engineer's interests, job placement includes choices in design, construction, project management or research. These young engineers coupled with the seasoned veterans provide an experienced, stable engineering capability prepared to meet any challenge the Navy faces.

The success that the Navy has experienced in ocean facilities design and construction in the past decade is directly attributed to the integration of its personnel assets in both the technical and operational commands. All facility design and construction planning is done by the Ocean Engineering and Construction Project Office, and coordinated closely with the fleet unit tasked to perform the work. For relatively routine construction projects, technical engineering support to the fleet unit is provided by a field engineer deployed with the unit. For ocean engineering projects involving complex facilities and significant logistics support, an "ad hoc" organization is established integrating parts of the technical and fleet commands with an ocean engineering officer in charge. And for projects involving advanced state-of-the-art systems or construction techniques, research engineers from the Navy technical laboratory commands are added to the organization to provide the additional special expertise needed. Thus, organizational flexibility provides the means of bringing together those parts of ocean engineering capability to satisfy all Navy requirements. This also serves to enhance communication between the technical and fleet commands resulting in a more effective capability development program to meet future ocean facility requirements.

Technology/Engineering Base

The oceans are considered by some to be the last frontier. The lack of ocean engineering technology maturity may be cause enough to believe them to be right. In particular, the technology for performing ocean facilities construction, just in the last decade, has progressed from simple hand tool capabilities to complex electro-hydraulic systems able to perform work with significant increases in efficiency. Technology developments are continuing to accelerate and yet man's ability to explore or perform work on the seafloor is still very limited.

The Navy, with its limited resources available for capability development, can not pursue inclusive technology development. Rather specific technologies critical to the Navy's ability to perform its mission receive the bulk of the resources. For ocean facilities, the Navy's efforts have been concentrated in ocean engineering research, and facility design criteria and ocean construction methods development.

Research - The technological base of knowledge necessary to design, construct, maintain and repair ocean structures which support Navy missions has been the principal development area. This includes: (1) materials technology, principally metals and concrete; (2) geotechnical engineering in support of seafloor foundation and trafficability design; (3) anchoring and mooring for structure fixity; (4)

facility structural concepts design including evaluation of environmental forces; and (5) diver tools, systems, power sources and construction techniques to improve man's ability to perform work in a hydrospace environment. This development effort accomplished in the past fifteen years has significantly increased the Navy's capability to acquire and maintain ocean facilities in a more reliable and efficient manner.

Navy contributions to technology transfer from these efforts includes but are not limited to the use of concrete for structure design to 3000 foot depths, acrylic material technology for submersible hulls and viewports and hyperbaric chamber windows, propellant embedment and drag anchor technology, three dimensional numerical models for structure/platform motion and stress analysis and a large number of diver tools and work systems. Research is continuing in the decade of the 1980's with the emphasis concentrated on inspection, maintenance and repair technology for the Navy's ocean facilities valued at over 4 billion dollars. Diver tools continue to be a major portion of this effort with the development of seawater hydraulics technology being the most significant contribution to the technology.

Design Criteria - Expanding the technology base for development sake is valued, but the end product must be improved capability in the design of facilities, systems, hardware or construction methods. The criteria for design of shore facilities is centuries old and has been refined in the crucible of time. Whereas ocean facilities design criteria began with modified bridge design technology and is barely a few decades old. Catastrophic failures has shown that ocean facility design criteria has not reached an equivalent maturity.

The US Navy individually and in association with the offshore industry has directed its efforts toward improving and documenting ocean facility design criteria. The Naval Facilities Engineering Command has developed, issued and continues to revise numerous design manuals for use by Navy engineers and government contractors. Also through close cooperation with professional society committees and task groups, the Navy is supporting the development of ocean industry design criteria and standards. These efforts coupled with an evolving, experienced engineering staff have greatly increased the Navy's capability to reliably design and construct ocean facilities.

Construction Methods - Terrestrial construction methods for facilities like its associated design criteria are well proven, efficient and standard. Ocean facilities construction does not enjoy this capability maturity. As a consequence each construction project must be carefully evaluated. In particular, the construction technique/method must be trade-off against the structure design limitations to optimize both and result in a successful installation. This necessarily forces the construction and facility design engineers and planners to be integrated as a team in the early stages of a facility project development. Construction plans and facility designs must be evaluated continuously and iterated to achieve not only the facility objectives but more importantly to reduce the installation risks to an acceptable margin.

To compensate for the lack of maturity in ocean construction methods and to some extent engineering experience, each major construction project executed by elements of the Ocean Facilities Program has been thoroughly documented in the past decade. This

repository contains information on various construction techniques used to meet facility requirements and lessons learned to correct deficiencies in the construction system or method. This documentation is particularly useful to young engineers and greatly helps to compensate for their lack of field experience.

Ocean Construction Equipment

Prior to 1972, most construction and installation of ocean facilities done within the Navy either by contract or Navy personnel required the design and assembly of a construction system. This system consisted of equipment normally designed for terrestrial construction use mixed with platforms and marine equipment. Many of these equipments used as is or modified for the tasks were not designed for use at sea. Thus, a risk to the construction process was added which impacted both safety and reliability of the facility installation. On occasion, when the facility value was large enough to warrant the cost, the construction system was specially designed to satisfy that particular installation need. The cost for design and fabrication of the construction system had to be amortized against the project; therefore, the project suffered an added cost burden. Additionally, the project was burdened with the test and evaluation of the new construction system and any costs to refine and correct system deficiencies.

To eliminate these problems, NAVFAC embarked on a long term program to acquire an inventory of coordinated specialized equipments. These equipments were selected either off the shelf or specially built to have individual as well as system performance capability necessary to afford the Navy a low-risk and economical ocean construction capability.

The benefits achieved by a centralized pool of equipment are many. Primarily it provides an economical and responsive capability for all construction requirements whether involving a rapid response to an emergency repair situation or for normally scheduled projects. Additional benefits in reduction or elimination of construction risks are afforded by having equipments which have been designed for use at sea and whose performance characteristics have been carefully specified and tested to meet ocean construction project requirements. Standardization of these equipments provides an added benefit of operator familiarity with the equipment thus, reducing risks due to lack of operator skill levels.

The Construction Equipment Inventory (OCEI) is centrally managed and maintained by the Chesapeake Division, Naval Facilities Engineering Command and has a current value of well over twenty million dollars. These equipments are housed at a facility located in Norfolk, Virginia and consist of cranes, winches, specialized diver tools, mooring systems and components, cable handling systems, electrical/electronic testing hardware, navigation systems, propulsion and positioning systems, underwater inspection systems and facility components. The single largest piece of equipment is the Ocean Construction Platform SEACON which is a unique platform capable of being dynamically positioned in the ocean to perform work.

Equipment requirements for the OCEI are carefully coordinated with the organic allowance of the Underwater Construction Teams (UCTs) as well as other Navy equipment pools to provide the Navy with a comprehensive ocean construction capability.

Through centralized management of personnel engineering/technical base development and equipment acquisition, NAVFAC's Ocean Facilities Program is providing the Navy with a highly reliable and cost effective ocean engineering and construction capability. Design and construction of ocean structures to meet stringent performance requirements, severe environmental conditions and minimum life cycle cost represents a continual challenge when viewed against a constantly shrinking resource base. But, the challenge is being met with a dedicated team of Navy planners, engineers and technicians supported by a highly skilled cadre of ocean engineering professionals from industry.

OCEAN FACILITY DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION

Many of the ocean facility requirements are unique to the Navy and have resulted in precedent setting designs and construction techniques. Requirements for future Navy facilities are also forcing the development of innovative facility concepts as well as advancing the engineering/technology base. Some of these facility projects and capability advances will be documented in the paper such that others may benefit from the information exchange.

Fleet Training, Readiness and T&E Facilities

Many of the Navy ocean facilities support fleet readiness training and weapon system performance assessment. Categorically, these type of facilities represent a large portion of Navy ocean facility assets. By their nature, they are also the most difficult to plan, design and construct to meet facility performance and life cycle cost requirements.

Ideally, fleet readiness training facilities should be co-located with large concentrations of fleet units, such as home port bases, to minimize cost, logistic support and limit ship time away from home port. Similar arguments can be made from weapon system test and evaluation facilities. However, functionally these type facilities require acoustically quiet sea conditions, unhindered use of large ocean areas and, for safety reasons, separated from large population centers and transportation lines of communication. Thus, facility performance requirements are quite often incompatible with facility location requirements necessitating trade-offs to be made between both requirements to arrive at an acceptable solution. Engineering solutions to some of these type facility problems are discussed.

Tactical Air Combat Training System (TACTS) - TACTS provides realistic training for pilots through electronic tracking of high speed aircraft and electronic simulation of ordnance firing under combat conditions. The first of these systems was installed in the desert at Yuma, Arizona. However, all Navy and Marine Corps pilots can't go to Yuma for training. Rather, TACTS facilities are required within operational flight distance of Naval and Marine Corps Air Stations dispersed throughout the United States and its territories. But air stations are generally located near population centers and sonic booms created by high speed aircraft are environmentally unacceptable. Thus, TACTS facilities are limited to ocean locations thirty miles from shore.

The East Coast-TACTS was the first of these type facilities to be built. Completed in 1977 and located off of Kitty Hawk, North Carolina it presented some unique problems for which solutions had to be developed. Four structures were required to support the electronic equipment for tracking the aircraft.

Additionally, these structures must be high enough and extremely rigid to maintain microwave data links between the structures and from a master station to shore. Further, the structures must sustain all environmental conditions including hurricanes without effecting system operation and require a minimum of maintenance over their twenty year life. To compound the problem, these were to be the first structures installed in 100 feet of water and 30 miles from shore on the East coast of the U.S.

The structure design selected over numerous other alternatives was a triangular configuration templet secured to the seafloor with piles driven through the three templet legs to 275 feet below the seafloor. After welding the piles to the templet, a super structure rising 75 feet above sea level was installed and welded in place. Because of their triangular configurations these structures are very rigid and have provided a very cost effective solution to TACTS requirements. Operational down time due to facility problems has been nil and electronic systems, powered by solar cells, have functioned satisfactorily. An underwater inspection of the four towers conducted five years after installation showed the structures to be performing satisfactorily and the cathodic protection system functioning adequately to protect the structures. Several small cracks were found in a high stress joint but are not significant enough to affect integrity of the structure.

As a result of a growing requirement to provide TACTS type training, more facilities are required off the East, West and Gulf Coasts of the United States. Site planning for these facilities has identified the need for structure designs compatible with water depths to several hundred feet on the continental shelf and several potential sites will require designs compatible with depths to 6000 feet or greater. Structural design technology resulting from the offshore petroleum industry should be adequate to satisfy Navy continental shelf requirements. However, TACTS sites having water depths of several thousand feet are a problem for which no long term facility solution presently exists.

Buoyant structures have been used at some locations but their performance has not been acceptable. Microwave transmission links are disrupted by buoy motion and system accuracy is effected by the large watch circles of the moored platforms. Further, buoy moorings have failed repeatedly causing temporary loss of capability and high maintenance costs. Engineering studies and industry-wide experience have defined the limit on mooring life to be approximately five years although industry is currently seeking to extend this to about seven years. A twenty year design life is currently not within the state-of-the-art.

Research has been initiated to develop compliant ocean structure designs for the 6000 foot depths that satisfy the stability requirements of geodetically referenced range instrumentation as well as meet long term facility survivability requirements. Innovative platform and mooring designs will be necessary to successfully meet this fleet requirement.

Navy Underwater Tracking Ranges - Like TACTS, underwater ranges provide a capability to track multiple targets in a volume of space. Acoustical techniques are used for underwater ranges in lieu of electronic methods used in TACTS facilities. Both systems function using similar tracking and triangulation algorithms. The underwater tracking ranges located in acoustically quiet areas provide the Navy

with the capability to test the performance of ship-board and aircraft offensive and defensive systems including firing exercise weapons. Test and evaluation of new weapon systems leading to production decisions are also conducted on these type ranges.

The functional performance of underwater tracking ranges, in part, is based on the ability to place acoustic sensors on the seafloor or suspended in the water column at precise predetermined locations. The ocean engineering associated with this requirement involves surveying the seafloor to determine the optimum locations for the sensors, designing and fabricating the sensor support structures and undersea cable data links to shore, and finally designing the construction system to reliably place the sensor at its selected location.

Acoustic sensor support structures span the gamut from simplified bottom mounted space frames to the more complex multiple leg structures with fixed or movable arms to support sensors at precise distances above the seafloor. Design requirements for these structures include sensor positional accuracy, material selection to avoid acoustic interference as well as being corrosion resistant, foundation considerations and installability under adverse sea-state conditions.

The structural design for the short base-line tracking system in use at the St. Croix, Virgin Islands underwater range is one of the most unique designs accomplished by the Navy. The short-base line system requires five hydrophones to be located at the corners of a thirty foot cube with a tolerance of one-eighth inch. Four hydrophones form a thirty foot square plane and the fifth hydrophone is positioned on the Z-axis thirty feet above one of the corners hydrophones. The hydrophones in the horizontal plane are located twenty feet above the seafloor. The design of a support structure to be placed in water depths of 3000 feet represented a significant challenge in view of the tolerance for hydrophone placement and structure size and weight impacts on handling and installing it under dynamic sea conditions.

The resulting design was a steel structure consisting of component parts which could be assembled to form a compact folded twenty foot configuration or unfolded and locked into its installed configuration of thirty foot square and fifty feet tall. The base of the structure formed a twenty foot square to which were attached four foldable hydrophone support arms, a foldable space frame to support the Z-axis hydrophone and four foldable legs. With the legs folded, the acoustic hardware was easily installed on the arms and Z-axis frame. Surveying of the hydrophones to achieve the precise thirty foot spacing was also done in this configuration. Installation of the structure was accomplished with the legs and Z-axis extended and the horizontal hydrophone arms folded. This afforded protection to the delicate hydrophones while passed them through the dynamic sea-air interface. After overboarding the structure and lowering it to a depth of approximately sixty feet, divers descended and opened the arms locking them into final position. After checking for structural integrity and performance of installed hydrophone systems, the structure was lowered to the seafloor and positioned using sophisticated acoustical techniques. Signal cables were layed from each structure to a shore terminal and connected to data processing systems.

Sea conditions at the St. Croix range are benign such that the undersea cables require little to no

stabilization in the near shore region. However, at other range locations such as Kauai, Hawaii and elsewhere, near shore wave conditions have caused major cable damage including severing of some signal cables. These conditions have fostered the development of numerous cable stabilization techniques including use of split pipe, rock bolts, grouting and fiberglass bags placed around the cable into which concrete is pumped. The selected stabilization technique is determined by the site prevailing sea and geotechnical conditions.

Future fleet training and weapon system test and evaluation needs require larger underwater tracking ranges necessitating design of facilities for water depths to 20,000 feet. Sensor support structure designs should not be impacted except to force more stringent control on structure weight and size. However, installation techniques and construction systems for these depths will require innovative thinking and designs. Due to prohibitive costs for repair, increased sensor and undersea cable systems reliability will also be required. Designs for ranges in 14,000 feet of water are currently underway by the Navy for installation in the mid-1980's.

Magnetic Silencing Facilities - Similar in function to tracking ranges, magnetic silencing facilities require the installation of sensors on the seafloor at precise locations. Likewise data is transmitted to shore data processing facilities via undersea cable. The primary differences are the type of sensors and magnetic silencing facilities are located in harbors, thus, in much shallower water depths. Also the sensitivity of the undersea sensors places tighter tolerance on the positional location accuracy of each sensor as well as the relative position of all sensors to each other.

Two types of facilities are required to provide a magnetic silencing capability for surface ships and submarines. These are degaussing facilities and deperming facilities. Degaussing facilities are used to measure ship and submarine magnetic signatures and have sensors located in harbor channels. Deperming facilities are used to alter the magnetic signature of a ship or submarine and as such require a pier structure to which the ship can be held in place while the treatment is done. These facilities consist of a single or double sided pier, a matrix of bottom sensors and cabling both bottom layed and wrapped around the ship to correct measured signature deficiencies. Due to material permeability requirements structural components of these facilities have been limited to treated timber for the past thirty years. Because treated timber is highly susceptible to marine bores and fungus damage, maintenance of these facilities has been high. But recent engineering studies, capitalizing on advances in materials technology, have defined improvements that can be made which will greatly reduce maintenance and life cycle costs and enhance fleet readiness.

The bottom mounted magnetic sensors for both degaussing and deperming facilities have for many years been installed on treated timber piles or in non-metallic tubes. Today fiberglass tubes are jettied into the seafloor in which the magnetic sensors are suspended. A special jig has been developed which can be placed on the seafloor and leveled in two directions to achieve the 2-3 degree vertical tolerance. Horizontal tolerances of 3 inches are achieved with specially designed spar buoy used to translate surface first order geodetic positional references to the seafloor. This is done by correcting for the horizontal offset at the bottom of the

spar buoy due to its imperfect verticality measured electronically. Once the sensor bottom position has been determined the special jig is positioned and leveled to an designed tolerance by a diver and the fiberglass tube jettied into the bottom to a selected elevation. This technique has been used to install a large number of sensors in San Diego harbor and proven highly controllable and effective. The technique will be used to install hundreds of new sensors at Navy degaussing and deperming facilities as these facilities are upgraded over the next five years.

The most significant problems experienced with regard to magnetic silencing facilities have been maintenance of the structure and the labor intensive operation associated with wrapping the ship with cable in order to treat it. Timber piling and fendering have an average life of 7-10 years and deck structures 14 years. Pier structures are very fragile and, subjected to repeated ship berthing, suffer damage due to impact loads. Wrapping the ship with cable requires extensive amounts of manpower including divers to haul the heavy cables around the ship and interconnect them. Life expectancies of these cables is low due to handling and abrasion from ship bottoms. All in all facility and operational improvements are both necessary and required.

Recent engineering studies have been concluded that address these problems and provide solutions. The overall objective of this effort was to develop a deperming facility concept achieving required functional performance at the lowest capital, maintenance, and operating cost with minimum risk to the ship and facility. Using a decision tree evaluation procedure, pier structural materials and concepts were evaluated to select the best material followed by cable handling concepts, and finally integrating these decisions into numerous facility configuration concepts to arrive at the optimal facility.

The engineering analysis showed that application of a relatively new steel, NITRONICS "32" stainless steel, using pre-cast prestress and concrete technology would provide a cost effective solution to the pier structure problems. Service life of greater than thirty years can be expected with this technology while still meeting the non-magnetic facility criteria. Cost studies have also shown that on a first cost basis the concrete structure is competitive with treated timber and on a life cycle basis concrete is less than half the cost of timber.

Using numerical models to determine the effectiveness of suspending the cables normally wrapped around the ship, variable spacing and cable sizing were tested against performance criteria. The results showed that substantial design freedom was available in sizing and spacing the cable loops and that suspending the cable was a practical alternative. Structural concepts for suspending the cables were developed and integrated with the pier concepts. The resulting recommended design for all future deperming facilities is a double sided reinforced prestressed concrete pier structure with fixed cabling suspended from non-metallic high guyed poles to allow deperming of both surface ships and submarines. This facility would effectively reduce the time required to deperm a ship or submarine from four days to less than one day. Designs of future deperming facilities are expected to incorporate these new concepts for pier structure and cable handling.

Mooring Facilities

In support of fleet requirements, the Navy has

mooring facilities located in every ocean region in which the fleets operate. These facilities range from a simplified single point mooring to very complex twenty-two leg floating drydock moorings. Although not as technically complex as the design of fleet training, readiness and T&E facilities, moorings, nevertheless, require careful attention to detail on their design and installation to avoid weak links. Failure of any part of the mooring, any weak link, can result in a multi-million dollar ship finding itself unsuspectingly aground with serious damage to its hull and propulsion systems. Loss of the ships capability and cost of the repairs can far exceed the cost of a economically designed mooring.

Recognizing a shortfall in the technology base for mooring design and mooring components, the Navy has dedicated resources over the past decade to vastly improve its capability in this area. Three major improvements to the technology base have been made that significantly enhances the Navy's mooring design capability. These are: (1) a family of validated computer models ranging from simplified static solutions to complex three dimensional models to calculate dynamic effects of loads and displacement on multiple leg moorings; (2) a family of Propellant Embedment Anchors (PEA) ranging from 10 Kips to 150 Kips of holding force for use in all seafloor conditions except rock; and (3) a comprehensively validated data base of conventional anchor performance for both Navy and commercial anchors. This latter effort has resulted in numerous design changes to existing anchors which has greatly improved their efficiency. All of this work was accomplished by the Naval Civil Engineering Laboratory at Port Hueneme, California.

Application of this new technology has been rapid, fostered by continual communication and cooperative spirit between the research and design communities. Design manuals are yet updated but facilities are already in place designed with the new technology. Eleven special moorings were designed and installed in Diego Garcia harbor during 1980-81 which used eighty-one PEA's. The PEA's were shot thirty feet into the coral seafloor and interconnected to form mooring legs capable of sustaining 300 Kip loads. Each anchor was load tested to its 150 Kip limit which validated design performance. The moorings were designed using the computer models to exercise various loading and configuration combinations to optimize the mooring design as well as assure performance against worst environmental conditions. These moorings have recently been inspected and found to be performing satisfactorily.

In Holy Loch, Scotland a floating drydock moored with twenty-two legs was experiencing larger than normal excursions in its watch circle. Computer modeling based on positional data provided from underwater inspection of the twenty-two legs showed anchors were dragging and the mooring design needed improvements. Using the computer model, numerous options were considered and a modified design selected. During June/July 1983, each of the twenty-two legs of the mooring were retrieved, inspected and the conventional anchors modified based on the NCEL research results. The legs were reinstalled, anchors set and the mooring pretensioned to designed loadings which is anticipated to result in reduced mooring excursions.

This overall improvement in mooring technology has significantly enhanced the Navy's capability to design and construct mooring facilities. Research effort is continuing to further refine design criteria and to improve mooring component performance.

Waterfront and Harbor Facilities

The waterfront and harbor facilities of the Naval shore establishment represent an investment of greater than 4 billion dollars. Because of the environment in which these facilities exist, they have the highest percentage of maintenance and repair for all type facilities. And because a large portion of these facilities are underwater, inspection to determine maintenance and repair requirements is most difficult to say the least.

Deterioration of structural elements, hidden both by turbid harbor water as well as external surfaces has gone undetected for years resulting in some cases of unexpected catastrophic facility failure. The key to improved maintenance and repair management, readiness assessment, and prevention of catastrophic failure is improved facility inspection and condition assessment. This is one of the Navy's highest priorities and to which significant resources are dedicated both for research and conditional assessment of facilities.

Technology and hardware to perform underwater inspection of structural members is very limited. In most cases inspections are limited to random sampling using visual techniques and physical measurements of the members. Ultra-sonic techniques for measurement of metal thickness and sounding techniques for measuring surface hardness as well as gauging pile soundness are coming more into use. However, validity of inspection results are questionable due to data scatter and lack of data repeatability. The largest problem facing both the Navy and commercial industry is the lack of ability to efficiently inspect a timber, concrete or composite pile. Surface damage is obvious and visually obtainable. What's hidden within the piles normal surface exterior is elusive and yet to be detected to an acceptable level of accuracy by any on-the-shelf hardware.

In the interim, Navy underwater construction technicians are being trained and commercial engineering firms with diving capability are being contracted to inspect Navy waterfront and harbor facilities. The facility conditional data base continues to be expanded and updated and inspection techniques and methods are being revised to improve results and efficiency. It is hoped that within the decade of the 1980's, efficient and effective underwater inspection techniques and hardware will become a reality.

SUMMARY

The Navy's ocean facilities capability including the personnel, technology/engineering data base and ocean construction equipment that comprise this capability have been reviewed. Ocean facilities and ocean technology, some unique to the Navy, have been briefly discussed and evaluated. Much of the technology developed by the Navy for ocean facilities design, construction, maintenance and repair has been made available to industry and the Navy continues to cooperate on technology transfer. Discussion of several facility projects has demonstrated how this technology is being applied to Navy requirements. The Navy continues to apply its resources to solving problems and to expanding the technology base for ocean engineering and remains a leader in this ever expanding frontier.

REFERENCES

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